

Studies on the Behaviour of Uni-bivalent Salts in Aqueous Solution. Part I. Potassium, Ammonium, Sodium, and Lithium Sulphates and Determination of Standard Electrode Potential of $\text{Hg} | \text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{SO}_4^{2-}$

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The study of the cells of types (a) and (b) shows that sulphates of potassium, ammonium, sodium, and lithium are completely dissociated in aqueous solution up to 0.1 *M*. The study of the cells of types (c) and (d) confirms this view. In these cells 'M' stands for potassium, ammonium, sodium, or lithium and 'C' for concentration in g. moles/litre. The standard electrode potential of the half cell, $\text{Hg}/\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{SO}_4^{2-}$, is found to be -0.6025 volt at 35°.

(a) Hg	$\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{M}_2\text{SO}_4$ (C ₁)	salt bridge	$\text{M}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4$ (C ₂)	Hg
(b) Hg	$\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{M}_2\text{SO}_4$ (C ₁)	$\text{M}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4$ (C ₂)	Hg	
(c) Hg	$\text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{MCl}$ (2C)	saturated KCl bridge	$\text{M}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4$ (C)	Hg
(d) Hg	$\text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{MCl}$ (2C)	$\text{M}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4$ (C)	Hg	

Righellato and Davies studied the dissociation of sulphates of K, Na, and Li (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 26, 592) by the conductance method and computed the dissociation constant of

to be 1.51×10^{-1} , 2.0×10^{-1} , and 2.29×10^{-1} respectively. They used some assumptions and approximations in their work. Their ideas have been checked with potentiometric measurements in the cells of the types :

(a) Hg	$\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{M}_2\text{SO}_4$ (C ₁)	salt bridge	$\text{M}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4$ (C ₂)	Hg
(b) Hg	$\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{M}_2\text{SO}_4$ (C ₁)	$\text{M}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4$ (C ₂)	Hg	
(c) Hg	$\text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{MCl}$ (2C)	saturated KCl bridge	$\text{M}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4$ (C)	Hg
(d) Hg	$\text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{MCl}$ (2C)	$\text{M}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4$ (C)	Hg	

(M stands for K, NH₄, Na, or Li)

EXPERIMENTAL

Mercurous sulphate from redistilled mercury was prepared by the electrolytic method of Hullet (*Phys. Rev.*, 1911, **32**, 257). It was washed with approximately 2*N*-H₂SO₄ and stored under H₂SO₄ of the same concentration.

Mercurous chloride was prepared by adding a KCl solution to a solution of mercurous nitrate. The precipitate was washed with distilled water till free of nitrate, dried, and rubbed with pure mercury.

Stock solutions of K₂SO₄, (NH₄)₂SO₄, Na₂SO₄, KCl, NH₄Cl, and NaCl were prepared from B.D.H. AnalaR samples by directly weighing the salts. The strength of the sulphate solution was verified gravimetrically as barium sulphate. A stock solution of lithium sulphate was prepared from E.P. lithium sulphate and its strength was determined by estimating the sulphate gravimetrically as above. A stock solution of lithium chloride was prepared by adding a weighed amount of dry lithium carbonate (E.P., E. Merck) to an exactly equivalent amount of dilute HCl (C.R.E. Merck). Other solutions used in the experiments were prepared by diluting the stock solutions. Double distilled water was used in all experiments.

Cell vessels and salt bridges used and the method of checking of the half cells were the same as reported previously (*this Journal*, 1951, **28**, 683). For studying the E.M.F. of the cells of type (a), the two tested half elements, having different concentrations of M₂SO₄, were joined through a salt bridge consisting of saturated KCl or KBr. The E.M.F. values of the cells are recorded in Table I.

In cells of type (b) the two half elements having different concentrations of M₂SO₄ were joined through a U tube (*ibid.*, 1954, **31**, 490). The E.M.F. values are shown in Table II. The results on the cells of type (c) are shown in Table III and that of type (d) in Table IV.

In these studies, the E.M.F. readings were taken in duplicate at 35° ± 0.1° and in every case the duplicates agreed within 0.2 mv.

TABLE I
Cell : type (a).

Conc. of sulphates.		E.M.F. with		Calc. E.M.F.	Diff. of columns (4) & (5).	E.M.F. with		Calc. E.M.F.	Diff. of columns (8) & (9).
C ₁ .	C ₂ .	KBr bridge.	KCl bridge.			KBr bridge.	KCl bridge.		
		Potassium sulphate.				Lithium sulphate.			
0.10 <i>M</i>	0.02 <i>M</i>	10.1mv	10.2mv	10.3mv	0.1mv	10.0mv	10.1mv	10.3mv	0.2mv
0.10	0.04	5.5	5.7	4.9	0.8	5.2	5.3	4.9	0.4
0.10	0.06	3.1	3.2	2.6	0.6	2.7	2.9	2.6	0.3
0.10	0.08	..	1.4	1.3	0.1	1.3	1.5	1.3	0.2
0.08	0.02	8.6	8.9	9.0	0.1	8.4	8.8	9.0	0.2
0.08	0.04	4.1	4.2	3.6	0.6	3.6	3.9	3.6	0.3
0.08	0.06	..	1.6	1.3	0.3	1.6	1.9	1.3	0.6
0.06	0.02	7.4	7.5	7.7	0.2	7.9	8.0	7.7	0.3
0.06	0.04	2.3	2.5	2.3	0.2	2.2	2.4	2.3	0.1
0.04	0.02	..	5.5	5.4	0.1	5.1	5.1	5.4	0.3

Av. 0.31

Av. 0.29

TABLE I (contd.)

0.10 M	0.02 M	..	Ammonium sulphate.			Sodium sulphate.			
			10.3 mv	10.2 mv	0.1 mv	10.2 mv	10.2 mv	10.2 mv	0.0 mv
0.10	0.04	..	5.4	4.9	0.5	5.2	5.5	4.9	0.6
0.10	0.06	3.0 mv	3.1	2.6	0.5	..	3.0	2.6	0.4
0.10	0.08	1.3	1.3	1.3	0.0	..	1.5	1.3	0.2
0.08	0.02	8.8	8.9	8.8	0.1	8.2	8.6	8.8	0.2
0.08	0.04	4.1	4.1	3.6	0.5	3.8	4.0	3.6	0.4
0.08	0.06	..	1.5	1.3	0.2	..	1.6	1.3	0.3
0.06	0.02	7.4	7.5	7.7	0.2	..	7.2	7.7	0.5
0.06	0.04	..	2.5	2.3	0.2	..	2.5	2.3	0.2
0.04	0.02	5.3	5.3	5.4	0.1	4.7	4.8	5.4	0.6
Av. 0.24						Av. 0.34			

TABLE II

Cell : type (b).

Molar conc.		E.M.F. (in mv)			E.M.F. (in mv)			E.M.F. (in mv)			E.M.F. (in mv)		
C_1	C_2	Obs.	Calc.	Diff.	Obs.	Calc.	Diff.	Obs.	Calc.	Diff.	Obs.	Calc.	Diff.
		Potassium sulphate.			Ammonium sulphate.			Sodium sulphate.			Lithium sulphate.		
0.04	0.02	10.5	10.5	0.0	9.9	10.6	0.7	..	..	..	7.5	7.6	0.1
0.06	0.04	5.7	6.0	0.3	5.5	5.9	0.4	4.5	4.9	0.4	4.0	4.2	0.2
0.08	0.06	4.2	4.2	0.0	3.9	4.1	0.2	3.2	3.4	0.2	3.0	2.9	0.1
0.10	0.08	3.1	2.8	0.3	2.9	2.8	0.1	2.6	2.3	0.3	2.3	2.0	0.3

TABLE III

Cell : type (c).

Molar conc.		Obs. E^*	Calc. $-E_{Cl^-}$	$-E_{SO_4^{2-}}$	Molar conc.		Obs. E^*	Calc. $-E_{Cl^-}$	$-E_{SO_4^{2-}}$
SO_4^{2-}	Cl^-				SO_4^{2-}	Cl^-			
				K ₂ SO ₄ and KCl		(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ and NH ₄ Cl			
0.02	0.04	0.3099 volt	0.3565	0.6664	0.02	0.04	0.3113 volt	0.3565	0.6678 volt
0.04	0.08	0.3223	0.3393	0.6616	0.04	0.08	0.3224	0.3393	0.6617
0.05	0.10	0.3261	0.3339	0.6600	0.06	0.12	0.3297	0.3294	0.6591
0.07	0.14	0.3322	0.3258	0.6580	0.07	0.14	0.3320	0.3288	0.6578
0.08	0.16	0.3339	0.3226	0.6565	0.08	0.16	0.3344	0.3225	0.6570
0.10	0.20	0.3386	0.3173	0.6559	0.10	0.20	0.3383	0.3173	0.6556
				Na ₂ SO ₄ and NaCl		Li ₂ SO ₄ and LiCl			
0.02	0.04	0.3104	0.3565	0.6669	0.02	0.04	0.3100	0.3565	0.6665
0.04	0.08	0.3220	0.3393	0.6613	0.04	0.08	0.3221	0.3393	0.6614
0.06	0.12	0.3295	0.3294	0.6589	0.05	0.10	0.3253	0.3339	0.6592
0.08	0.16	0.3344	0.3226	0.6570	0.07	0.14	0.3311	0.3258	0.6569
0.10	0.20	0.3380	0.3173	0.6553	0.10	0.20	0.3372	0.3173	0.6545

TABLE IV

Cell : types (c) and (d).

Molar conc.		E'' of (type c).	E''' of (type d).	$E'' - E'''$.	Molar conc.		E'' of (type c).	E''' of (type d).	$E'' - E'''$.
SO_4^{2-} .	Cl^- .				SO_4^{2-} .	Cl^- .			
Potassium sulphate and potassium chloride.					Ammonium sulphate and ammonium chloride.				
0.02	0.04	0.3099 volt	0.3034 volt	0.0065 volt	0.02	0.04	0.3113 volt	0.3049 volt	0.0064 volt
0.04	0.08	0.3223	0.3154	0.0069	0.04	0.08	0.3224	0.3263	0.0061
0.05	0.10	0.3261	0.3200	0.0061	0.06	0.12	0.3297	0.3231	0.0066
0.07	0.14	0.3322	0.3257	0.0065	0.08	0.16	0.3344	0.3279	0.0065
0.08	0.16	0.3339	0.3274	0.0065	0.10	0.20	0.3383	0.3319	0.0063
0.10	0.20	0.3386	0.3316	0.0070	..	..	..	..	..
Mean $E_J = -0.0066$ volt.					Mean $E_J = -0.0064$.				

TABLE V

Value of $E^\circ_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ calc. from that of $E_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ recorded in Table III.

Sulphate.	$-E_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$	$-\frac{RT}{2F} \log_e a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$	$-E^\circ_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$	Sulphate.	$-E_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$	$-\frac{RT}{2F} \log_e a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$	$-E^\circ_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$
Potassium sulphate.				Sodium sulphate.			
0.02M	0.6664 volt	0.0638	0.6026 volt	0.02M	0.6669	0.0638	0.6031
0.04	0.6616	0.0585	0.6031	0.04	0.6613	0.0585	0.6028
0.05	0.6600	0.0570	0.6030	0.06	0.6589	0.0560	0.6029
0.07	0.6580	0.0553	0.6027	0.08	0.6570	0.0545	0.6025
0.08	0.6565	0.0545	0.6020	0.10	0.6553	0.0534	0.6019
0.10	0.6559	0.0533	0.6026	..	..	..	..
Mean $E^\circ_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}} = -0.6027$ volt.				Mean value of $E_0 = -0.6026$.			
Ammonium sulphate.				Lithium sulphate.			
0.02M	0.6678	0.0638	0.6040*	0.02	0.6665	0.0638	0.6027
0.04	0.6617	0.0585	0.6032	0.04	0.6614	0.0585	0.6029
0.06	0.6591	0.0560	0.6031	0.05	0.6592	0.0570	0.6022
0.07	0.6578	0.0553	0.6025	0.07	0.6569	0.0553	0.6016
0.08	0.6570	0.0545	0.6025	0.10	0.6545	0.0533	0.6012†
0.10	0.6556	0.0534	0.6022	..	..	..	..
*Mean value of E_0 excluding the one asterisked = -0.6027.				†Neglected while taking the mean. Mean $E^\circ_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}} = -0.6024$ volt.			

N.B. Mean for all the four salts is -0.6026 volt.

DISCUSSION

Assuming that the liquid junction potential is eliminated by the salt bridge used, the E.M.F. values of the cells of type (a) for a particular salt can be represented by the equation :

$$E = \frac{RT}{2F} \log \frac{C_1 f_1^{2-}}{C_2 f_2^{2-}} \quad \dots (1)$$

where C_1 and C_2 and f_1^{2-} and f_2^{2-} are respectively the concentrations and activity coefficients of the sulphate ion for various ionic strengths calculated from the mean activity coefficients

(Landolt-Börnstein, "Physikalisch-Chemische Tabellen", Roth and Scheel) of the sulphate and chloride concerned by the procedure followed earlier (*ibid.*, 1951, 28, 683). Having known the activity coefficients, f_1^{2-} and f_2^{2-} , E , is calculated from equation (1), by assuming M_2SO_4 in solution to be dissociated completely to 0.10 M . The calculated values of E , recorded under columns 5 and 9 of Table I, agree fairly well with the observed E.M.F. shown under columns 3 & 7 (sat'd. KBr bridges) and 4 (sat'd. KCl bridge). Elimination of the liquid junction potential by saturated KCl or KBr bridge in the cells of type (a) has always been found nearly the same.

The E.M.F. of the cells of type (b) can be represented by

$$E' = \frac{3}{2} \cdot \frac{RT}{F} \cdot t^+ \cdot \log \frac{C_1(f^{\pm})_1}{C_2(f^{\pm})_2} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where t^+ is the transport number of metal ion and C_1 , C_2 , $(f^{\pm})_1$ and $(f^{\pm})_2$ are respectively the concentrations and mean activity coefficients of M_2SO_4 at two different concentrations. The ionic conductances of K^+ , NH_4^+ , Na^+ , Li^+ , and $\frac{1}{2} SO_4^{2-}$ have been calculated to be 87.9, 88.5, 61.1, 49.7, and 95.0 at 35° from the data recorded by Glasstone (*Electro-Chemistry of Solutions*", 1945, p. 72). Transport numbers of these cations in their sulphates are found respectively to be 0.481, 0.482, 0.393, and 0.335 from the above data. With the transport numbers and the value of mean activity, the values of E' in these sulphates have been calculated from equation (2). The calculated values of E' are found to agree well with the observed data (Table II).

The study of the cells of types (a) and (b) conclusively demonstrates complete dissociation of the four sulphates in solution up to 0.10 M . To check this further and to determine the standard electrode potential, ($E^\circ_{SO_4^{2-}}$) of $Hg | Hg_2SO_4, SO_4^{2-}$, measurements of the E.M.F. values of the cells of types (c) and (d) were undertaken.

Assuming that the liquid junction potential is eliminated by saturated KCl bridge, the E.M.F. (E'') of the cells of type (c) is represented by

$$E'' = E_{Cl^-} - E_{SO_4^{2-}} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where E_{Cl^-} is the E.M.F. of the $Hg | Hg_2Cl_2, MCl$ half element and $E_{SO_4^{2-}}$ is that of the $Hg | Hg_2SO_4, M_2SO_4$ half element. The assumption about the elimination of liquid junction potential in cells of type (c) can be tested.

The E.M.F. (E''') of cells of type (d) are represented by

$$E''' = E_{Cl^-} - E_{SO_4^{2-}} + E_j \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

where E_j is the liquid junction potential developed between M_2SO_4 and MCl solutions. Equations (3) and (4) evidently show that if saturated KCl is able to eliminate the liquid junction potential, the difference of E''' and E'' should be equal to the value of E_j . E_j can be calculated from Henderson's equation, which reduces to the following form in the present conditions :

$$E_j = \frac{RT}{F} \cdot \frac{V_{Cl^-} - \frac{1}{2} V_{\frac{1}{2}SO_4^{2-}}}{V_{\frac{1}{2}SO_4^{2-}} - V_{Cl^-}} \log \frac{U_{M^+} + V_{Cl^-}}{U_{M^+} - V_{\frac{1}{2}SO_4^{2-}}}$$

In the above equation V_{Cl^-} and $V_{\frac{1}{2}SO_4^{2-}}$ represent the ionic (equivalent) conductance of Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} , and U_{M^+} represents the conductance of K^+ or NH_4^+ , depending on the type of cell used. Table IV shows that the average difference between E'' and E''' in the case of potassium salt is 6.6 mv and in ammonium salt, 6.4 mv. The calculated value of E_j for Henderson's equation comes out to be 6.1 mv in both cases. Hence, if there is any liquid junction potential, it is not likely to be beyond 0.5 mv. It may be assumed that l.j.p. is eliminated by saturated KCl in cells of type (c). Since the E.M.F. of these cells has been calculated on the basis of K_2SO_4 being completely dissociated in solution up to a concentration of 0.1 M , it might be safely concluded that K_2SO_4 is completely dissociated up to that concentration.

The value of $E_{\text{Cl}^-}^\circ$ (standard electrode potential of $\text{Hg} | \text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{Cl}^-$) is known at 18° and at 25° . By extrapolation the value is found to be -0.2659 at 35° . Now

$$E_{\text{Cl}^-} = E_{\text{Cl}^-}^\circ + \frac{RT}{F} \log_e C_{\text{Cl}^-} \cdot f_{\text{Cl}^-}$$

The value of f_{Cl^-} for KCl , NH_4Cl , NaCl , and LiCl is taken to be the same as the mean activity coefficient of KCl at the same concentration. The value of E_{Cl^-} has thus been calculated (Table III). From this and the corresponding value of E'' , recorded in these tables, $E_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ has been calculated (Table III) and from the value of $E_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$, $E_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}^\circ$ has also been calculated in Table V by using the equation :

$$E_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}} = E_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}^\circ + \frac{RT}{2F} \log_e a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$$

The mean value of $E_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}^\circ$, taking the four salts into consideration, is 0.6026 volt. $E_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}^\circ$ can be also calculated in the four cases by using the Debye-Hückel limiting equation :

$$E_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}} = E_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}^\circ + \frac{RT}{2F} \log_e C_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}} - \frac{RT}{2F} 4A \times 2.303 \sqrt{\mu} + \frac{RT}{2F} B\mu$$

where $A = 0.516$ at 35° and by plotting

$$E_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}} - \frac{RT}{2F} \log_e C_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}} + \frac{2RT}{F} \times 2.303 A \sqrt{\mu}$$

against μ . The extrapolated values for K_2SO_4 , $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, Na_2SO_4 and Li_2SO_4 are -0.6026 , -0.6025 , -0.6021 , and -0.6023 volt respectively, the mean of which is -0.6024 volt. Mean of the two methods is -0.6025 volt. The agreement of the two methods is very satisfactory. Our use of activity coefficient and complete dissociation up to a concentration of $0.1M$ in case of the four sulphates seems to be justified.

Correction in the concentration of sulphate ion due to the solubility of mercurous sulphate in the various sulphates is negligible.

The value of $E_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}^\circ$ (-0.6025 volt) obtained in this work is 4.4 mv, lower than that obtained by Harned and Hamer (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 27) (-0.6070 volt at 35°), who determined $E_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}^\circ$ at 0° , 15° , 25° , 40° , and 60° and represented their results by an equation having two constants. Their experimental value at 40° is 0.59900 ; the value calculated by their equation is 0.60305 and the difference comes to 4.05 mv. Their results can be better represented by the three-constant equation :

$$E_t^\circ = 0.63495 - 6.093 \times 10^{-4} \times t - 1.5157 \times 10^{-5} t^2 + 1.9794 \times 10^{-7} t^3$$

Even with this equation the calculated value of E_{25}° comes to 0.61334 against the experimental value of 0.61514 and the difference is 1.8 mv. With three-constant equation, the value of E_{25}° comes to 0.6034 and differs from our value by 0.9 mv. When the difference between the calculated and observed values in Harned and Hamer's work comes to 4.05 mv with the first equation and 1.8 mv with the second equation, then the difference of 4.5 between the calculated value from the first equation and our value and the difference of 0.9 mv between our value and the value calculated from Harned and Hamer's work from the second equation becomes understandable. Hence our value (-0.6025) may be taken to be correct.

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